

SUMMARY

Circular aviation is responding to the societal demand for sustainable aviation. Green solutions connected to propulsion are one side of the proverbial coin. The other side encompasses circular economy approaches tackling resource consumption and emissions along the entire value chain, including production of aircraft, maintenance, and end-of-life solutions.

OBJECTIVES

The central approach of SUSTAINair is to substantially increase the sustainability of the airframe value chain achieving a paradigm shift in aircraft manufacturing. This includes:

- Circular design of individual components and joining technologies for airframe construction
- Real-time structural health monitoring of materials and joints during operations
- Improved maintenance and repair technologies to extend aircraft life-time
- Rivet removal demonstrator using robotics & water jet cutting for improved recovery of high-quality aluminum recycling materials

UP- and RECYCLING

- Upcycling of thermoset and thermoplastic production waste
- Inter-recycling of solid and liquid metals
- Inhouse recycling of production scrap

INDUSTRY

Economically viable automated aircraft fuselage dismantling and material separation

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE

Integration and development of novel sensors enabling real-time, onboard damage diagnosis and prognosis (SHM).

CIRCULAR DESIGN

Lightweight design meets: up-and recyclable materials and embedded functionalities for real-time onboard damage diagnosis and prognosis

JOINING FOR DISSIMILAR MATERIALS

Joining and repair technologies for similar and dissimilar aerospace grade material combinations.

ZERO WASTE ASSEMBLY

METALS: Advanced near-net shape manufacturing and additive manufacturing

COMPOSITES: Reducing in-house material waste

The circular economy is an approach to make the most out of resources by keeping them in use for as long as possible, thus increasing their total value throughout their life cycle.

EXPECTED IMPACT

- To reduce mass, improve fuel consumption and reduce emissions, SUSTAINair is operating on a multi-material design philosophy with novel metal alloys and composite materials. SUSTAINair joining techniques could ultimately eliminate the need for rivets all together.
 - To increase aerodynamic efficiency and maintain aircraft safety, SUSTAINair's integrated sensor technology will allow real-time, onboard damage diagnosis (SHM).
 - In pursuit of significant energy-saving and therefore environmental benefits, SUSTAINair is introducing industrially-viable flexible wing with morphing capabilities a reality.
 - The novel up- and recycling methods developed within SUSTAINair for both metal and composite aviation materials, will contribute to a major reduction of waste incurred during the manufacturing and end-of-life processes. Upcycling solutions will be developed for carbon- and glass fibre thermoset materials, as well as high-performance thermoplastic composites.
- ⇒ The SUSTAINair project aims to achieve 100 % recyclability of current aviation thermoset & thermoplast FRPs, and 100% utilization of parts due to condition-based maintenance.

Specifically, the SUSTAINair project aims to reduce costs:

- ⇒ in fuel consumption, due to multi-material approach
- ⇒ in thermoplastic parts due to upcycling techniques
- ⇒ for repair and maintenance due to zero-waste assembly
- ⇒ decrease the buy-to-fly ratio for aluminium close to 1
- ⇒ 50% decrease in titanium powder degradation
- ⇒ 8% take-off gross weight Moreover, the project aim is:
- ⇒ 50% increase in shear and fatigue joint strength
- ⇒ 3-factor increase in the value of end-of-life materials

In a post-COVID19 world, SUSTAINair is introducing the circular economy along the entire aircraft value chain, paving the runway to a more cost-effective, low-carbon economy.

CONSORTIUM

- AIT-LKR Leichtmetallkompetenzzentrum Ranshofen GmbH (Austria)
- Netherlands Aerospace Centre – NLR (Netherlands)
- DLR – Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (Germany)
- JOANNEUM RESEARCH (Austria)
- JKU Linz – Johannes Kepler University Linz (Austria)
- TU Delft – Delft University of Technology (Netherlands)
- INOCON Technologie GmbH (Austria)
- INVENT GmbH (Germany)
- DTC – Dutch Thermoplastic Components B.V. (Netherlands)
- RTDS Association (Austria)
- AELS – Aircraft End-of-Life Solutions (Netherlands)

PROJECT COORDINATION

- AIT-LKR Leichtmetallkompetenzzentrum Ranshofen GmbH (Austria)

